

SCHOOL LEADER'S RESOURCES MANAGEMENT AND ITS IMPLICATION IN ACHIEVING QUALITY OF WORK LIFE AMONG PUBLIC ELEMENTARY TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The role of the school leader in the management of resources today is more important, serious, and challenging in which teachers are directly involved. There are concerns in school resources management that need to be addressed to meet the needs of the teachers which may improve their quality of work life. Thus, this study focused on the school leader's management of resources and its impact on the quality of work-life among public elementary teachers. This descriptive and correlational study utilized one hundred twenty-five (125) public elementary school teachers from seven (7) selected public schools within Candelaria East District and conducted within the school year 2020-2021. A researcher-made survey questionnaire through google form was utilized as the primary instrument to gather the needed data for the study. The study revealed that school plant, human, and financial resources management as established by school leaders have a positive significant relationship with the level of satisfaction of the teacher- respondents in quality of work life. It shows that they practicing a good management strategy in their resources to provide quality of work-life for teachers in their respective schools. Moreover, to improve the teacher's quality of work-life, identify and try to address important needs through their experience in their work environment. Likewise, school leaders should emphasize the management of the human resource, particularly on the personnel management and employee's welfare, as these factors significantly predict the quality of work-life of teachers and must deal with new concerns and adjustments with regards to the management of resources in the new normal education system to improve their quality of work life.

Keywords: School Resources Management, School Plant, Financial Resource, Human Resource, Quality of Work Life